

APPLICATIONS OF HIGH THERMALLY CONDUCTIVE K1100X/RESIN SYSTEMS TO SPACECRAFT STRUCTURE AND EQUIPMENT

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ABSTRACT

During the last few years, the potential applications of highly conductive polymer composites to spacecraft structures and equipment has received great interest. Amoco's K1100X fiber is currently the only fiber available that, in a practical laminate form (pseudoisotropic), exhibits similar thermal properties to copper. In a unidirectional laminate form, moreover, the fiber exhibits a thermal conductivity 60% greater than pure copper. This paper reports on some specific properties of this material system and how it can be utilized on spacecraft structures and equipment to take advantage of its unique thermal characteristics.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this paper is to report on Composite Optics, Incorporated's (COI), efforts in developing applications for high conductivity polymer composite materials. Most of our work has centered around Amoco's K1100X fiber although some applications for Amoco's Thermalgraph® and E-System's TC1050 are being considered. Amoco's K1100X/resin system has great application potential for thermal management of spacecraft structures and equipment because of its high specific conductivity, namely, 344 W/m-k/g/cc (Reference 1). This value for a unidirectional laminate is approximately 7.6 times better than pure copper (45 W/m-k/g/cc) or approximately 5 times alloy aluminum (81 W/m-k/g/cc). Although these values for specific conductivity are reduced somewhat for pseudoisotropic laminates of polymer composite K1100X/resin system, values like 4.6 and 3.1 times higher, respectively, for copper and alloy aluminum, are still impressive.

The drawbacks for the K1100X/resin systems are its current high cost, low strength (especially compression) and that an applications "manual" is not included. COI and other fabricators and/or users of the material are finding ways to work around these drawbacks. COI's efforts in this respect are manifested in the applications discussion that follows.

APPLICATIONS

Although the applications presented here are in the thermal management of spacecraft, the principle of how to utilize the material effectively was learned in fabricating and testing a cardguide for a standard ATR (Air Transport Rack). The results of testing, accomplished by NAWC (Naval Air Warfare Center), are reported on below.

The spacecraft structure and equipment applications of K1100X/resin system that are of most interest to COI currently are Radiators and Conductors, Bus Structure, Solar Array Panel, Substrates (standard and photovoltaic), and Electronic Packaging.

Following a brief discussion of the ATR cardguide, these various spacecraft applications of K1100X/resin system will be discussed in greater detail.

ATR CARDGUIDE - The cardguide shown in Figure 1 was fabricated by COI to the exact dimensional requirements of Standard ATR aluminum alloy cardguides. Because the critical thermal conductivity path is from the cardguide rails (thin wall aluminum channels or tubes) to the heat exchanger (series of fins on back of panel), the material chosen was thin laminates of K1100X/cyanate with fibers oriented to optimize heat transfer.

FIGURE 1 Photograph of ATR Cardguide

The key to making this design work is the interfacing design of the K1100X fibers with the rails which can not be detailed for proprietary reasons. The results of this ATR cardguide are shown in Figure 2. Evident in this Figure is that the composite cardguide is operating at about 15-20°C cooler than the standard cardguide at each rail. A stabilized condition was reached for both cardguides before the individual rail temperatures were measured and recorded. NAWC personnel considered this a very significant reduction in the operation temperature of the cardguide.

FIGURE 2 Thermal Performance of COI Composite Cardage

SPACECRAFT RADIATORS AND CONDUCTORS. In this grouping of spacecraft components, there are a number of ways to utilize the highly conductive properties of K1100X/resin systems. Radiators, for instance, can be flat parallel panels attached to the outside of a spacecraft, or fins in the corners, or integrally a part of the structure as a side panel or a skin on an equipment deck.

Figure 3 illustrates this latter application. Likewise for conductors, a variety of ways to utilize K1100X/resin systems can be envisioned. Using the K1100X/resin system as a unidirectional or pseudoisotropic laminate, thin laminates bonded to more structural polymer composite materials and specifically designed joints may result in an optimum thermal management design (with cost being a consideration).

FIGURE 3 Concept Spacecraft Bus and Thermal Control Components

SPACECRAFT BUS STRUCTURE. Bus structures using honeycomb sandwich construction or spaceframe construction can be fashioned entirely, or in part, from K1100X/resin systems. The material cost for the spacecraft bus structure may be a very large number, but whether K1100X makes sense depends on specific mission requirements. Material cost, for example, may be insignificant compared to a need to utilize a more powerful rocket if a metallic spacecraft bus structure were used.

Regarding the issue of the low compression strength of K1100X/resin system in a spacecraft bus structure, it may, nevertheless, be suitable because the thermal requirements dictate skin thicknesses and that stiffness and strength requirements are a non-issue. In Figure 3, the spaceframe structure with shear panels on all sides could be fabricated from a K1100X/resin system.

SPACECRAFT SOLAR ARRAY PANEL SUBSTRATE. Utilizing K1100X/resin system for solar array panel substrates may make sense because the material's superior thermal conductivity can be effective in spreading the heat away from solar cells and radiating it off the back panel's surface.

Photovoltaic Technology is a suitable and interesting application for highly conductive composites. Figure 4 illustrates the functional parts of a photovoltaic panel. Figure 5 depicts the radiator and/or back structure of the photovoltaic panel.

FIGURE 4 Photovoltaic Panel Configuration
(Illustration Courtesy of AEC-ABLE Engineering)

NOTE: Receivers are mounted to strips of carbon-carbon, Thermalgraph®, or encapsulated TC1050 that provide a heatsink and radiation protection (if required) for the receivers.

Figure 5 Photograph of a Photovoltaic Panel Substrate (Fresnel Lens not installed)

• SPACECRAFT ELECTRONIC PACKAGING. The application of K1100X/resin system to spacecraft electronic packaging involves a number of interesting choices such as cards, heatsinks (or thermal cores), cardguides, cardcages (VME boxes), electronic housing and/or chassis (general).

CARDS and HEATSINKS (THERMAL CORE). For computer cards, any number of designs can be pursued because of the "individualistic nature" that exists in the spacecraft industry. Each has its own shape and thickness and interfacing method with cardguides or rails. K1100X/resin system could be used as a laminate or in combination with other materials for this application. COI has fabricated several different thermal core samples using combinations of materials to best satisfy necessary performance requirements. E-Systems is testing these thermal cores.

CARDGUIDE and CARDCAGES. The basic design COI built into the ATR cardguide (for aircraft application) was also built into the spacecraft type cardcage shown in Figure 6. This cardcage is all K1100X/954-3 graphite/cyanate except for the aluminum rails and internal frame structure. The rails/frame are off-the-shelf aluminum extrusions. This cardcage weighs about one-half that of an equivalent sized all-aluminum cardcage. Because of the significance of this application, Sandia National Laboratory has performed some benchmark testing to assess the performance characteristics of this cardcage with respect to conventional all-aluminum cardcage test. A description and results follow.

CARDCAGE TEST RESULTS. A series of thermal-vacuum tests were conducted at Sandia National Laboratory's Space Simulation Thermal-Vacuum Test Facility to compare the thermal performance of the COI composite cardcage, shown previously in Figure 6 for a conventional aluminum cardcage used to house electronics for a space-type application (Figure 7). The COI cardcage is constructed such that it dissipates heat to the environment via thermal radiation. The aluminum cardcage has relatively thick walls and a large contact area with the chamber plate compared to the COI cardcage. Thus, heat conduction is more prevalent in the aluminum cardcage versus the COI cardcage. Although in effect, the outer surface area (for radiating) of the COI cardcage was 28% larger than the aluminum cardcage and was painted white.

FIGURE 6

Photograph of a Composite Cardcage

FIGURE 7

Prototype Aluminum Cardcage

For the aluminum cardcage, the flat bottom side was screwed to the chamber plate with a thermal interfacing material compressed in the faying surface to improve heat conduction to the plate. The COI cardcage had very little area in contact with the chamber plate and no thermal interfacing was attempted. Even attachment to chamber plate was via nylon screws.

There were three prototype boards constructed for the COI tests as shown in Figure 8. Each board used a 3.2 W heat source using 8 wire-wound resistors that were adhesively bonded to the board using Delta Bond. An aluminum plate was adhesively bonded to the top of the resistors to confine the heat to a finite area and simulate an electronics component.

The first board in Figure 8(a) is 0.1524 cm thick G-10 board with a one ounce flashing of copper on each surface. The second board shown in Figure 8(b) is a COI composite board constructed of 0.0254 cm thick G-10, 0.0508 cm thick K1100X, and 0.0508 cm thick NX50. The third board tested in Figure 8(c) is a combination of the first two boards adhesively bonded together. In each test, the side of the board with the heat source was pressed against the aluminum rails. Calmark wedge clamps were used to clamp the boards to the aluminum rails as shown in Figure 8 (a), (b), (c), (d).

FIGURE 8. Various Mounting Arrangements for Prototype Boards in Cardcages

The COI cardcage was attached to the chamber heating/cooling plate using four tabs located at each corner of the cardcage. Since the tab contact area is small, heat loss from the cardcage is primarily thermal radiation to the surroundings. Two tests were performed for each board to verify repeatability. The first and third boards were also tested with the clamps removed to determine the significance of using the clamps.

A G-10 prototype board similar to the first board (Figure 8d) was used in the aluminum cardcage tests. The same test conditions used for the COI cardcage were applied in the aluminum box tests. Two tests were performed to test repeatability and a third test with the clamps removed.

All the tests were performed at a chamber pressure of 10^{-6} Torr, and base plate and shroud temperatures of approximately 27°C until steady-state temperatures were obtained (2 hours). The heat source power was 3.2 W using an external power supply.

The steady-state temperatures for the COI cardcage are shown in Tables 1 - Test Configuration. As expected, the heat source temperatures decreased from the G-10 to the G-10/composite board configuration due to the addition of higher thermal conductivity materials and a larger heat conduction cross-sectional area. Temperatures were lower in Test Configuration (b) and (c) as compared to Test Configuration (a) due to the efficient heat spreading by the composite material. The rail, inner wall, and outer wall temperatures in Table 1 - Test Configuration (a), (b), and (c) remained approximately the same.

The results for the aluminum cardcage are given in Table 1 - Test Configuration (d). The heat source temperatures were 73°C, 20°C higher than the heat source temperatures for the G-10 board in Table 1 - Test Configuration (a). Thus, the COI cardcage design significantly reduces the board temperatures. It was also shown that clamping is vital to improved thermal conductivity (i.e., reduces temperature by 20°C or more at the heat source).

An advantage of the COI cardcage is that the inner surfaces are naturally black which provides a high infrared emissivity. In order to produce this property for an aluminum cardcage interior, the inside surfaces need to be either painted black, which requires a special masking of the part to avoid paint screw holes or bare metal interfaces, or anodizing the aluminum, a chemical process.

TABLE 1 TEST CONFIGURATION

TC No.	LOCATION	TEST CONFIGURATION			
		Figure 8 (a)	Figure 8 (b)	Figure 8 (c)	Figure 8 (d)
1	Heat Source	53.0	46.5	43.7	73.1
2	Board	44.0	32.8	34.0	34.8
3	Board	38.5	32.2	32.8	34.0
4	Board Back	51.4	34.4	33.6	44.0
5	Rail	30.0	29.9	29.5	27.2
6	Inner Wall	29.6	29.6	29.1	—
7	Rail	30.1	29.8	29.4	27.2
8	Inner Wall	29.6	29.7	29.1	27.2
9	Outer Wall	28.6	28.9	28.7	28.2
10	Outer Wall	28.3	28.6	28.6	28.2
11	Outer Wall	27.8	27.9	28.0	28.2
12	Shroud	26.5	26.2	26.8	25.3
13	Heat Source	53.4	46.9	44.5	72.6
14	Base Plate	25.9	25.7	25.9	25.8

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This discussion has touched on only a few of the many applications possible using highly conductive K1100X/resin system. Future applications should abound as material information gets into the hands and minds of those who are concerned about Thermal Management issues.

A series of thermal-vacuum tests were conducted to compare the thermal performance of the COI cardcage with a prototypical aluminum cardcage. Even with the thermal radiative design of the COI cardcage, lower heat source temperatures were obtained than the aluminum cardcage. Adding a composite heat spreader to the board also lowers the heat source temperature and increases the reliability of the electronics component.

REFERENCES

1. Space Materials Update Seminar; "K1100X Prepregs for Thermal Management and 954-3 and 954-3 Cyanate Ester Prepregs"; Anaheim, CA; April 12, 1994.